

**CHARACTERISTICS OF THE “NASHINSKI” SPEECH: COMPARISON WITH
THE STATE OF THE BOSNIAN LANGUAGE**

**“NAŞİNSKİ” SÖYLEMİNİN ÖZELLİKLERİ: BOŞNAM DİLİNİN DURUMUYLA
KARŞILAŞTIRMA**

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ABSTRACT

In the of Prizren and its surrounding areas, including the regions of Zupa, Gora and Podgor a distinctive speech known as “Naşinski” or “Naşki” is still preserved by the local inhabitants. The speakers make a clear distinction between their native “Naşinski” speech and the other languages they learn and use later in life. Despite external influences, “Naşinski” remains actively used throughout Gora, Zupa and Podgor, as well as by some of the population that has moved to Prizren and other cities. While interactions with other languages have led to changes in everyday “Naşinski” speech, folk creativity has largely resisted these external influences. The richest and most authentic form of “Naşinski” is preserved in the region’s folk oral traditions.

Keywords: Prizren, Zupa, Naşki native speech, language preservation, folk creativity, oral traditions, linguistic influences, local inhabitants, cultural identity.

ÖZET

Prizren ve çevresindeki Zupa, Gora ve Podgor bölgelerinde, yerel halk tarafından hala “Naşinski” veya “Naşki” olarak bilinen kendine özgü bir konuşma biçimi korunmaktadır. Konuşmacılar, ana dilleri olan “Naşinski” ile daha sonra öğrendikleri ve kullandıkları diğer diller arasında net bir ayrım yapmaktadırlar. Dış etkilere rağmen, “Naşinski” Gora, Zupa ve Podgor’da ve Prizren ile diğer şehirlere taşınan nüfusun bir kısmı tarafından aktif olarak kullanılmaya devam etmektedir. Diğer dillerle etkileşimler günlük “Naşinski” konuşmasında değişikliklere yol açmış olsa da, halk yaratıcılığı bu dış etkilere büyük ölçüde direnmiştir. “Naşinski”nin en zengin ve en otantik biçimi, bölgenin halk sözlü geleneklerinde korunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Prizren, Zupa, Naşki yerel dili, dilin korunması, halk yaratıcılığı, sözlü gelenekler, dilsel etkiler, yerel halk, kültürel kimlik.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the city of Prizren and its surroundings, in the regions of Župa, Gora, and Podgor, a specific speech known as “*Našinski/Naški*” is preserved in verbal communication by the local inhabitants. They make a distinction between this speech and other non-native languages they learn and use later in life.

Despite various influences, “*Našinski*” is still actively used in all parts of Gora, Župa, and Podgor, as well as among some of the population who have moved to Prizren and other cities. In interactions with other languages, changes in everyday “*Našinski*” speech are evident, while folk creativity has resisted almost all external influences. The richest and purest “*Našinski*” speech is preserved in folk oral creativity.

The region in the linguistic rhomboid of Prizren-Kukes-Debar is primarily historically complete, but in the past, this unique linguistic system differentiated into three sub-dialects, namely:

1. The Župa and Podgor dialect (southeast of Prizren), which can be considered the most progressive (having undergone the most changes);
2. The Gorani speech type (centred in the municipality of Dragash), which can be divided into two types: upper valley and lower valley. The difference is phonological;
3. The speech in the Kukes area in Albania, i.e., Gorani villages around Kukes. This speech is the least progressive (retaining the oldest words in speech).¹

A significant number of phonetic values in the “*Našinski*” speech are completely unknown to contemporary Bosnian language (semi-vowel, diphthongs, consonant Dz) or belong to its distant linguistic past.

The speech of Župa has been very little scientifically researched, mainly by Serbian researchers. They mostly claim ownership of this speech and exclusively use informants from areas where Serbian population resides in describing it. The speech of the majority Bosniak population in Župa is sporadically and incidentally researched.

The speech of Župa has not been thoroughly researched, although some researchers have touched upon its characteristics in monographic treatments or synthetic discussions. Milivoj Pavlović briefly touched upon the speech of the non-Serbian population of this region in the book “*Govoru Sretečke Župe*” (*The Speech of Sretečka Župa*)².

Several authors have written about the speech of Gora, among whom Božidar Vidoevski, Radivoje Mladenović, Alija Džogović, Nazif Dokle, Sadik Idrizi, and others stand out.

Due to the constant movement of the population in these areas and frequent contact with speakers of other non-Slavic languages, the “*Našinski*” speech has been subjected to constant influences from almost all Balkan languages.

The “*Našinski*” speech often experienced various interlingual interferences, leading to changes in its phonetic, morphological, and syntactic systems that are not recognized by the standard Bosnian language.

¹ Alija Džogović, *Mostovi, čitanka za 9. orijentacioni razred*, Libri shkollor, Priština, 2005.

² Milivoj Pavlović (1891-1974) has published the book “*Govor Sretečke Župe*” in 1939. in Belgrade.

The “Našinski” speech is spoken in the following settlements:

- a) **Gora:** Restelica, Brod, Kruševo, Globočica, Zli Potok, Vraništa, Mlike, Bačka, Dikance, Kukaljane, Ljubošta, Leštane, Dragaš (Krakošta), Radeša, Orčuša, Dornji Krstec, Gornji Krstec, Dornja Rapča, Gornja Rapča, Šištejec, Borje, Zapod, Pakiša, Orgosta, Crnjeljevo, Košarišta, Orešek, Očikle, Urvič and Jelovjane;
- b) **Župa:** Gornje Ljubinjje, Dornje Ljubinjje, Rečane, Planjane, Manastirica, Mušnikovo, Nebregošte, Lokvica, Gornje Selo, Drajčiči, Jablanica and Pousko.
- c) **Podgor:** Ljubizda, Grnčare, Skorobišta and Novo Selo.

2. GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE NAŠINSKI SPEECH

The inhabitants of the mentioned areas speak a specific Slavic speech they themselves call “*Našinski jezik*” (Našinski language). This is the speech they use in their mutual communication, while in official use, as a literary language, in administration, and education, it was Serbian, or in the last twenty years, Bosnian language.

The Našinski speech is a mixture of Slavic languages: Serbian, Bosnian, and Macedonian, with influences from Turkish, Albanian, and even Bulgarian, with a specific dialect and accent.

In some of its dialects, this dialect preserves the old semi-vowel (Ѣ), which in all other Štokavian dialects evolved into **A**: *dъn, tъnъk* (in literary language: dan, tanak). The vocal **L** in one part of this dialect gave **Iu**: *'dlug, slunce, sluz'a*, while in another part it remained unchanged: *pln, dlг, slnce, slza* (in literary language: *pun, dug, sunce, suza*). In one part of this dialect, **Ć** and **Đ** are pronounced as **Č** and **Dž**: *kuča, medža* (in literary: *kuća, međa*). Some dialects of this dialect have turned **L** at the end of the word into **V/F**: *rkov/f, rabotav/f* (lit. *rekao, radio*). The consonant **H** is almost neutralized in some parts: *straota* (lit. *strahota*), *uvo* (lit. *uho*), while in other parts it is well preserved. The infinitive form has disappeared, the future **I** is formed using **će** + present: *će rabota* (lit. on *će raditi*), it does not know the past participle, and there is only one accent.

The language of the population of the Šar Mountains geographical region is linguistically homogeneous, specific, coherent, and *independent* of related linguistic systems - Macedonian and Serbian. It is specific in its complete linguistic being: phonological-phonetic, morphological, syntactic, and lexical.

These differences can be observed and confirmed through detailed analysis of historical diachrony and synchrony, and even more so on contemporary linguistic material.

In Serbian linguistic science, this speech zone is treated as one of the Serbian dialects or the oldest Serbian language, while in the Macedonian dialect map, this speech area is treated as Northwestern Macedonian speech.

3. PHONETIC SYSTEM

The Našinski speech, in terms of some phonetic features, differs from all surrounding dialects on both the Serbian and Macedonian sides, as it developed under the strong influence of non-Slavic languages - Turkish, Arabic, Aromanian, and Albanian.

The majority of today's Slavic languages have completed the establishment of historical grammatical reasons for the transformation of Old Slavic (Common Slavic) vocal system, and they have their own photograph of the vocal state. In the Našinski speech, remnants of the Old

Slavic (Common Slavic) vocal system are still present (semi-vowels, diphthongs, vocal l and r, etc.).

The consonant system of the Našinski speech developed under the strong influence of non-Slavic languages - Turkish, Arabic, Aromanian, and Albanian. Some phonemes occur with various allophonic variations, and phonological neutralization is observed. Within the Našinski speech, differences in the distribution of consonants are noticeable, so that in some speech types, certain phonemes have almost disappeared, while in others they are stable. The state of the sound system of a language or dialect usually contains basic phenomena for understanding internal phonetic problems, as well as for determining the degree of stabilization of the process itself in the case of linguistic or dialectal mixtures. To conduct a descriptive analysis of the Našinski speech, we need to see its relationship to the sounds of surrounding speeches.

Vowels in the Našinski speech are normally formed. In the speech of Župa, diphthongs occur. Diphthongs (double vowels) can be found in many words:

- diftong **aa**: *ícaa, ova, taa*;
- diftong **ee**: *raboteeći, sedeeći, mišljeeći, zeeno*;
- diftong **ua**: *mua, tvua, njegua, svakua, kažualje, utepuav, utepuala*;
- diftong **oi**: *mostoi*;
- diftong **ue**: *čuek, tue, puet, nečuek*;
- diftong **ae**: *drugaeći, ripaet*;
- diftong **ai**: *dunjaište*;
- diftong **ie**: *niena (nijedna)*;
- diftong **oa**: *proadet, doadet*.

To properly pronounce diphthongs, it is best to hear the native pronunciation of those words and observe the characteristics in their pronunciation. In the Gora speech, diphthongs are only known in the Brod dialect type. In addition to full-form vowels, the Našinski speech also uses a semi-vowel, which is typical in certain positions and is vocalized to a lesser or greater extent in others. In this speech, the sound of the semi-vowel “*is formed by a sudden, rapid opening of the vocal cords, their explosion*” (Aleksandar Belić³). This semi-vowel is found in words like: *đn, sn, tvnina, kna...*

In addition to this semi-vowel, there is also a semi-vowel with some vocalization, i.e., with partial, weak, or strong vibration of the vocal cords. Examples include: *vbzdn, dbnbs*.

In addition to this semi-vowel, there is also a semi-vowel with the **O** color - *sâm, nesâm*, and sometimes it has the value of **reduced O** - *som, nesom*. Labial sounds (**W**) and palatal **J** are found in these speeches only as a new phenomenon and thus represent just one alternative form of *v/i-dvoraj, dvorowi*, to some extent spread type: *koj, svakoj, nekoj, tujka, jope*. Vocalic **R** is typical as in all surrounding speeches: *brgo, drvo, prv, crn*. In the Našinski speech, the sound **L** in some words, before the vowels **E** and **I**, often changes to soft **Lj**: *ljis, ljisica, ljepo, ljice*. The consonant **Lj** is normal in cases like *Ljubinja, kolješ, nedelja, sljive*. This phenomenon is also present in other speeches and is believed to have developed under the influence of the Albanian language. For consonants **Ć** and **Đ**, we can notice that they are stable as in all surrounding speeches. However, the pronunciation of these sounds differs in individual villages. In some villages, we have the pronunciation of softened sounds, which is a characteristic of the Macedonian speech. Thus, we have softened pronunciation: *kuća,*

³ Aleksandar Belić (1876 – 1960) he was a philologist and linguist, professor and rector of Belgrade University, president of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts and a member of many academies in Yugoslavia and abroad.

ćaramida, oće, neće, povraćaj, knoći, veđe, jende, sunder. In the majority of the inhabitants of Župa, the articulation of consonants is not observed, so affricates are pronounced equally regardless of whether they are soft or hard in pronunciation, and the same is true in writing. The consonant **F** is normal, as in general in all speeches where it is heard, for example in the word *fala* instead of *hvala*, and in words of foreign origin, it is literally heard: *fes, fenjer*. In all dialects of the Bosnian language, the sound **H** is consistently preserved. In the Bosniak written tradition and in the language of writers, it is also regularly used: *halva, Hasan, truhla, haljina, dođoh, pođoh*. It is very stable in the Bosnian language, among other things, because the Arabic language has a very frequent use of this sound (there are three types of **H** consonants in Arabic), which also influenced its preservation in dialects of the Bosnian language. This preservation is particularly achieved through the Qur'an and its constant recitation in Muslim prayers. The sound **H** consistently occurs primarily in orientalisms (Turkisms), where it is etymologically appropriate: *halal, haber, Habiba, Hajrija, halva...* When we talk about the sound **H** in the Našinski speech, we can say that this sound is very rarely used, even in words where it is etymologically appropriate. In the sound system of the Bosnian, Serbian, Croatian languages, there is no sound **DZ**, which is one of the characteristics of the Našinski speech. This sound is present in the Macedonian language (**S**) but also in the Albanian language (**X**). There are several words in which this sound is used. Such words are: *Dzuko, dzvono, dzebe, dziri, modzok, dzid. Dzvezda...* Probably under the influence of Albanian and Macedonian, this sound has been retained in the speech, mostly in the speech of older people. This sound is replaced by the sound **Z** in the Bosnian language.

3.1. Palatalization

In Bosnian language, when talking about the consonant “**J**” in the past, when it stood after another consonant, there were always some phonetic changes. When it comes to alveolo-palatal consonants, it was always lost behind them. The reason for this is that they are softened sounds, so they contained that consonant within themselves. The same is true now in Bosnian, Serbian, and Croatian. When the consonant “**J**” was found after “**D**,” “**T**,” “**Z**,” “**L**,” and “**N**,” it gave new consonants “**Đ**,” “**Ć**,” “**Ž**,” “**Lj**,” and “**Nj**”: “*mlad+ji*” = “*mlađi*,” “*ljut + ji*” = “*ljući*,” “*brži*,” “*viši*,” “*bjelji*,” and “*tanji*.” When we talk about palatalization, where alveolo-palatal consonants together with the sound “**J**” give alveolo-palatal consonants, in the Našinski speech, we encounter a mixture. Thus, in some words, we can encounter completed palatalization: “*kazati*” > “*kažem*,” “*mljeti*” > “*meljem*,” “*doći*” > “*dođem*,” but there are also dual forms: “*poći*” > “*pođem*” and “*pojdem*,” “*doći*” > “*dođem*” and “*dojdem*.” In collective nouns where “**T + J**” and “**D + J**” give the sounds “**Ć**” and “**Đ**,” there are also elements of palatalization, but also words with incomplete palatalization. So, we have “*braća*,” “*bratoj*,” “*bratovi*,” “*drveće*,” “*lišće*,” but also “*lisje*” or “*ljisje*,” “*pijenje*” and “*pjesje*,” “*smijenje*” and “*smejenje*,” “*pjenje*” and “*poenje*,” “*viđenje*,” “*mesenje*,” “*sirenje*,” “*trčenje*,” “*oranje*,” “*branje*,” “*svirenje*.” When we talk about the second palatalization, where the consonant “**J**” after labial consonants in modern Bosnian language gives “**Lj**,” the picture is different. We have such palatalization in a small number of words: “*divlji*,” “*divlja*,” “*divljo*,” although the forms “*divji*,” “*divja*,” “*divjo*” are also known. For the noun “*zdravlje*,” we have dual usage: “*zdravlje*” and “*zdravje*,” for example: “*idi mi soz zdravlje*,” and “*idi mi so zdravje*.” We also have dual forms for the nouns “*grojze*” and “*grozje*,” “*lojze*” and “*lozje*.”

The consonant “**J**” after “**B**,” “**P**,” “**V**,” and “**M**” does not change to “**Lj**,” and also “**D**,” “**T**,” and “**Z**” do not change to “**Đ**,” “**Ć**,” and “**Ž**” in front of “**J**”: “*ograden*,” “*zaroben*,” “*izguben*,” “*zagraden*,” “*grobje*,” “*ljisje*,” “*snopje*,” “*prigotven ruček*,” “*lovenje*,”

“naprajeno,” “poklopeno,” “kupen,” “potopen,” “ocepen,” “spremen,” “vaden,” “izvaden,” “zagraden,” “nagraden,” “sedenje,” “sudenje,” “vraten,” “vrten,” “kite,” “nakiten,” “besen,” “obesen,” “gasen,” “mesen,” “mesenje,” “kosenje,” “zborenje,” “vozenje,” “pazaren”...

In the Našinski speech, we have words with a significant softening of sounds “**Nj**” and “**Lj**”: “branjet,” “ženji,” “punji,” “napunji,” “činji,” “učinji,” “brašnjo” but also “brašno,” “snjek,” “snek” but also “snegoj,” “jasenj,” “kamenj,” “prstenj,” “korenj,” “ravenj,” “pesnje,” “voljet,” “odalječiv,” “odeljiv,” “podeljet,” “zaljepiv,” “mišljiv,” “mišljelje,” “molji,” “moljet,” “zasilji,” “osolji,” “žalji,” “palji,” “ljep,” “mljeko.”

It is worth noting that in this speech, there are words with complete and incomplete palatalization.

3.2. Assimilation of consonants by voicing

In a spoken sequence, two consonants of unequal voicing often appear next to each other. This results in articulatory difficulties in their pronunciation. These difficulties are traditionally termed as difficult or heavy pronunciation in grammatical terminology. When two consonants of different voicing are adjacent, they assimilate in voicing. The one that comes first in the sequence assimilates to the voicing of the other, turning into its counterpart. Regarding this phenomenon in the Našinski dialect, it can be said that it occurs in the same way as in the standard Bosnian language. Thus, we have:

dub > dupka, uz-put > usput, nož > nošče, svat > svadba, svadbarski.

There is no assimilation in words where there are semivowels: *sabrav, sabralje*. It should be noted that in this dialect, the consonant clusters *str* and *zdr* are very consistently preserved, so we have: *streća, Strecka, strami se, stramota, strede, sredina, sreda, stretnav, strečno, u sustrec*. In some cases, the **T** is lost from this consonant cluster, resulting in *sr*: *srećen put, sreda, sredina, zdrav, zdravje, zdrelo, uzdrelo*. From this, we look for similarities with other dialects. An example in the Tetovo dialect includes: *stramota, sredina, streća*; in the Ohrid dialect: *streda, streća*; in the Kičevo dialect: *strebren, streća*. This leads us to conclude that in these cases, the most influence comes from the Macedonian language.

3.3. Assimilation of consonants by place of articulation.

Assimilation of consonants by place and manner of articulation is a change that affects a significantly smaller number of sounds compared to assimilation of consonants by voicing. Its results are reflected in a considerably smaller number of examples in the Bosnian language. This assimilation is limited to:

- a) Stream dental consonants **S** and **Z**;
- b) To the stream posterior palatal consonant **H**; and
- c) To the sonant **N**.

Examples: *lišće > lišće, časćenje > čašćenje, mislju > mišlju; grožđe > grožđe, paznja > pažnja, voznja > vožnja, zelenbać > zelembać, stanbeni > stambeni, crmpurast > crmpurast.*

When it comes to this sound change in the Našinski dialect, it can be said that there are words where it occurs, as in the standard language, but there are also examples where it deviates from the standard. To illustrate this, let's look at some examples.

The consonant cluster **st** is still preserved: “*ostar noš*”. In this dialect, there is a transition from **S** to **Š** and from “**z**” to “**Ž**”. For example: “*pršče*”, “*poreždžja*”, “*prepašće*”, but also “*prepasće*”. The consonant cluster *slj* transitions to *šlj*: “*misljiv*”, “*mišljiv*”. However, such a transition does not occur before **Nj**: “*so nego*”, “*oz njega*”. Similarly, **V** before **C** and **K** transitions to an explosive **P** for example: “*kolepka*”, “*vrpca*”. The group **BN** remains unchanged: “*ozebne*”, “*ozebnav*”; the group **VN** is also unchanged: “*ravno*”, “*ravne*”, while with the group **VNJ** there are fluctuations: “*glavnja*”, “*plevnja*” but also “*pljevnja*”.

3.4. Metathesis

In the Našinski dialect, like in all Štokavian dialects, metathesis occurs quite frequently. For example, the word “*mogila*” can be compared to “*mogilka*” instead of “*gomila*.” There are many such examples: “*bajrak*” and “*bajraktar*,” “*pladne*” and “*plande*,” “*sorva*” and “*sovra*” (sofra). Here, it's worth mentioning the word “*mlanesta*” compared to “*nevesta*,” as well as the word “*Amberika*,” probably influenced by the words “*ambar*” and “*lamba*,” which retained the consonant cluster “**MB**.” The word “*lojze*” is compared to “*lozje*,” which has the same meaning. In the Restelica dialect, metathesis occurs in words like “*avla*” (halva) and “*svabda*” (svadba).

4. MORPHOLOGICAL SYSTEM

In the Našinski dialect, there has been a reduction in the number of case forms, a characteristic shared with neighbouring South Slavic dialects. This reduction is particularly evident in dialects near the Gora region, on both sides of the Šar Mountain. However, the number of case distinctions in the Našinski dialect, both in singular and plural, is greater than in most Macedonian dialects. The Našinski dialect preserves nominative, vocative, and dative cases in the singular, while in the plural, the case system is reduced to two forms: *nominative = vocative and dative*.

The use of the definite article in postposition is a feature of the Gora dialect. The Aromanian language, which strongly influenced the state of the Gora dialect, differs from other Roman languages in that the definite article is added as a suffix at the end of the noun, rather than preceding it, and changes through declensions along with the noun.

Comparative and superlative forms of adjectives and adverbs are analytical in the Našinski dialect, similar to neighbouring dialects. The comparative is formed by using *po + positive*, while the superlative is formed by using *naj + positive*.

In terms of verb forms, the following are used in the Našinski dialect:

- a) Simple: *present, aorist, imperfect, imperative, active and passive participles, present participle*.
- b) Compound: *perfect, pluperfect, future, potential (mood)*.

Infinitive forms, past gerund, and future II tense forms are not confirmed in conjugation. The loss of infinitive and its replacement with a periphrastic subjunctive construction *da + present or present tense*, the elimination of Slavic future tense, and the presence of the analytic perfect are among the features that classify the Našinski dialect as a language with a high degree of Balkanization.

5. LEXICON

The lexical aspect of the Našinski dialect represents an area that has been insufficiently explored, both in terms of the origin of the lexicon and its emotional-stylistic function and usage. This dialect has preserved many archaisms and fossilized Slavic lexemes. However, it has also absorbed many words from neighbouring non-Slavic languages, often indirectly and from distant and unrelated languages. This has enriched the Našinski dialect and provided speakers with a wide range of stylistic choices and nuanced expressions. Therefore, the Našinski dialect represents a distinct and rich lexical area.

The bulk of the lexicon of the Našinski dialect consists mainly of words of Slavic origin, with a significant number of borrowings from the Turkish language, as well as from other languages in the immediate and wider surrounding area. This dialect is characterized by the preservation and use of archaic vocabulary, as well as the ability to create and use various possibilities in deriving new words based on existing linguistic material.

In the Našinski dialect, there is a certain number of lexemes whose origin is difficult to determine. Some words present in the dialect have no equivalents in other languages or linguistic areas. For another group of lexemes, roots can be traced back to Balkan languages (Greek, Aromanian, Albanian, etc.), and possibly to “secret languages” used by various groups in a broader area (craftsmen's languages, Bosnian language, etc.).

In terms of the lexicon of foreign origin in the Našinski dialect, orientalisms (or Turkisms) are particularly notable – words that have entered the dialect from Oriental languages such as Arabic, Persian, or Turkish. Most often, these words have entered through the Turkish language, hence the term “Turkisms.” The Našinski dialect contains thousands of Turkisms, including root words and words that are carriers of basic meanings, as well as compounds and words that have arisen through arbitrary prefixation and suffixation.

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Over time, many orientalisms have undergone various semantic changes, partial or complete, which have resulted in polysemy and the establishment of new synonymic and antonymic relationships. Nevertheless, orientalisms have stood the test of time and are still preserved, not only in linguistic meaning but also in language usage, among various communities in the Našinski dialect area.

6. CONCLUSION

The dialects of Gora, Župa, and Podgor represent a distinct dialectological area that is interesting for studying the theory of language contact and language development in a foreign linguistic environment. This dialect has remained isolated and in a “frozen state” for centuries, but after the historical changes that have occurred in the Balkans over the past hundred years, it has found itself in a completely new and altered situation. Today, this dialect can serve as a valuable source of data for studying diglossia, bilingualism, language interference, as well as for other linguistic and sociolinguistic research.

The Našinski dialect is a mixture of dialects. While certain features are still preserved, we can also see the influence of recent dialectal processes that have occurred in evolutionary phases. The influence of different population mixtures and migration movements has led to the emergence of various processes in the dialect.

In communication, in addition to thirty sounds, the inhabitants also use two additional sounds - the semi-vowel and the consonant **Dz**. As for writing, the number of graphemes is the same as in the Bosnian language. The vowel and consonant composition differ from Bosnian in the Našinski dialect. Diphthongs are one of the characteristics of this dialect and

are pronounced in a specific way. The semi-vowel is often used in speech. Affricates are often mixed in speech, which is noticeable because their pronunciation is not taken into account. This is also reflected in writing, where these words lose their true meanings. The sound **H** is rarely used in its original position and is also lost in all positions. Another characteristic of the Našinski dialect is a sound that is not found in Bosnian. It is formed by merging the consonants **D** and **Z**, and is pronounced like **X** in Albanian and **S** in Macedonian. This consonant is not used in writing; instead, the sound **Z** is used. Among numerous researchers and linguists, there are still disagreements regarding this dialect, its origins, and its classification. It is essential for future researchers to definitively explain the claim of Bosnian linguists that it is the easternmost Bosnian dialect, Serbian linguists that it is the southernmost Serbian dialect, and Macedonian linguists that it is the northwesternmost Macedonian dialect. This can be achieved through comparative and contrastive analysis of empirical data in the field to affirm or refute the credibility of these claims.

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